

A Study of Guided Intervention as Adjunctive Therapy through Spiritual Energy Healing of the Universal Life Force 'Reiki' and the Eternal Vibration Rhythm of 'AUM' on Cancer Patients: A Case Series of Six Spectacular Journeys.

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ABSTRACT:

Objectives: Objective analysis and evaluation of the guided intervention as adjunctive therapy through Spiritual Energy Healing of the Universal Life Force 'Reiki' and the Vibration- Rhythm of 'AUM' on six Cancer Patients. **Methods:** The effect of the guided intervention was quantitatively mapped through the standard published questionnaire EORTC QLQ-C30 (version 3) as well as specific disease questionnaires EORTC QLQ-BR 23 for breast cancer, and EORTC QLQ- HL 27 for Hodgkin Lymphoma. The qualitative data were collected through interviews and their experiences. **Results:** Analysis depicts marked improvements in Functional Scales (physical functioning, role functioning, emotional functioning, cognitive functioning, social functioning), Symptom Scales (fatigue, nausea & vomiting, pains, dyspnoea, insomnia, constipation, diarrhoea, financial difficulties) and Global Health status parameters of quality of life among the respondents. Similarly, for the specific disease parameters of Breast Cancer and Hodgkin Lymphoma, the participants have reported definite improvements in Symptom Scales and functional scales. Qualitative analysis also indicates definite improvements in quality of life, getting rid of fear of death, the side effects of chemotherapy, radiation and other cancer-related treatments, regaining health holistically etc. **Conclusion:** Spiritual Energy healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM' is therapeutically highly effective as adjunctive therapy to ensure holistic and comprehensive health outcomes. Health practitioners should use these as adjunctive therapies to enable the patients to have sustained recovery and healthy living in the future.

Keywords: Cancer, 'Reiki', 'AUM', Quality of Life, Chemotherapy side-effects

INTRODUCTION:

BACKGROUND:

Cancer poses substantial challenges due to distress and trauma caused by physical cancer symptoms, subtle cognitive dysfunction and post-traumatic stress impairing the quality of Life. Most

importantly, side effects of chemotherapy, radiation and other conventional medical treatments cause critical challenges to the quality of life of cancer patients. The Spiritual Energy Healing through 'Reiki' and eternal 'AUM' Rhythm-Vibration, are recognized for their potential to add to recovery,

alleviate distress, trauma and pain as well as enhance emotional stability and mental strength. *This case series investigates the effects of Spiritual Energy Healing of combined 'Reiki' and 'AUM' on the quality of life, Physical functioning, Emotional functioning, Cognitive functioning, social functioning, Pain, Fatigue, Nausea, Dyspnoea, Appetite etc of six cancer patients, exploring the potential of these interventions as adjuncts to conventional cancer treatments.*

RATIONALE:

As per the Vedic Teachings and knowledge of ancient Indian Sages, AUM (ॐ, the Syllable OM) is the *Eternal Universal Vibration and Rhythm of Creation*. The Spiritual Attunement with 'AUM (ॐ)' is highly effective for inner transformation, strengthening willpower, mind power, cognition abilities, inner curative power for holistic health, Stress Management, inner wisdom and spiritual development. 'Reiki' is a Japanese word meaning the 'Universal Life Force Energy' referred to in *Vedic Hindu Scriptures* as 'Pran-Shakti'. It is also referred to as 'touch therapy' as it involves Spiritual Healing by laying a hand close to the person, the healee. Prior research on Spiritual Energy Healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM' on cancer patients has helped them to reduce pain, anxiety, and depression levels following regular sessions of Healing (1, 2). Combining 'Reiki' and 'AUM' is believed to create synergistic effects, facilitating deeper healing and transformative positive therapeutic effects of spiritual energy healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM', combined in the management of cancer as adjunctive therapies. In a study of holistic recovery through the intervention of Spiritual Energy Healing techniques through 'AUM' and 'Reiki' on cancer patients, it has been found that the techniques are compatible and adaptable to 92.8 % of the study population from all walks of life. The study confirms the definite potential of these Spiritual techniques to enhance the quality of life, mental health, mindfulness and reduce side effects of chemotherapy, as well as anxiety and fear of death (2,3). Patients who got 'Reiki' healing are reported to have higher self-efficacy with powerful effects of 'Reiki' intervention on mood, anxiety, and recovery than the patients who have lower self-efficacy (4). Other studies also show that 'Reiki' reduces fatigue and increases the quality of life among breast cancer patients who receive chemotherapy (5). 'Reiki' helps in regulating pulse rate and blood pressure while providing further relief to caregivers (6).

OBJECTIVE:

The objective of this research is to explore, map and establish the therapeutic impact of spiritual energy

healing through Universal Life Force 'Reiki' and Eternal Spiritual Rhythm 'AUM', combined, as adjunctive therapy on Cancer Patients at any stage of disease.

METHODS:

Design: Quantitative changes in patients' well-being and improvement were assessed by administering the EORTC QLQ-C30 (version 3) questionnaire, a validated tool for measuring the quality of life in cancer patients. Furthermore, specific disease questionnaires EORTC QLQ- BR 23 for Breast Cancer, and EORTC QLQ- HL 27 for Hodgkin Lymphoma were also administered. Qualitative data was collected through interviews and patient testimonials to provide a comprehensive understanding of the potential benefits of spiritual energy healing practices for cancer patients. The data was collected at intervals of every 30 days (one month) of intervention for consecutive three months.

Study population: Six (6) Cancer Patients were non-randomly selected from cancer treatment centres, representing diverse cancer types and stages. Those with severe cognitive impairments or inability to participate in spiritual healing sessions were excluded.

Demographic details of the selected samples are as below:

1. Patient 1- 70 years-Female Invasive Ductal Carcinoma - Metastatic breast cancer
2. Patient 2- 27 years-Female Classical Hodgkin Lymphoma - Refractory Stage IV
3. Patient 3- 43 years-Female Invasive Ductal Carcinoma - Stage II
4. Patient 4- 57 years-Female Breast Cancer - Metastatic
5. Patient 5- 55 years-Male-Colorectal Cancer-Moderately differentiated infiltrating adenocarcinoma of the colon (Dukes stage B)
6. Patient 6- 53 years-Male-Renal Cell Carcinoma - Metastatic

INTERVENTION:

The patients were attuned with the spiritual energy of 'AUM' and Universal life force 'Reiki' by chief resource person Dr M. K. Bimal, a Spiritual Scientist, Reiki' Grandmaster & Teacher, Spiritual 'AUM' Meditation Therapist.

ANALYSIS:

The quantitative data from the questionnaire and qualitative data collected through interviews were analysed and evaluated.

RESULTS:

Quantitative Data:

Intervention on Quality of Life among all cancer patients; assessed through EORTC QLQ-C 30 (version 3)

Functional Scale Values:

The research data of the functional scale (physical functioning, role functioning, emotional functioning, cognitive functioning, social functioning), of six cancer patients has been

reflected in Table A.1 placed below at the end. For all the respondents in Table A.1, the values of all functional scales were low or zero in the initial month, which steadily picked up, registering the maximum value of 100.00 in the post intervention 3rd month. In Emotional functioning values, pre-intervention values are exceptionally low, often zeros, which increase to 100 for all respondents during post-intervention.

Figure A: Mean of the Functional Scale Values of the Respondents

Figure A depicts that the mean values of the functional scales increase progressively after the intervention. For example, the Role functioning mean values have increased from 25.00 in the pre-intervention to 97.22 in the post-intervention third month. The mean values of the Emotional functioning and Cognitive functioning scale both attained the value of 100.00.

Symptom Scale Values:

The research data of the symptoms scale (fatigue, nausea & vomiting, pains, dyspnoea, insomnia, constipation, diarrhoea, financial difficulties) of six cancer patients has been reflected in Table B.1 presented below in the end. Table B.1 shows that all the symptom scale values declined progressively after the intervention of spiritual healing registering zero in the third month. For example, for Patient 1, the Fatigue scale value of 55.56 was reduced to zero in the Post-Intervention third month.

Figure B: Mean of the Symptom Scale Values of the Respondents.

In Figure B, it can be seen that in the 'pain scale', the mean value is 83.33 in the Pre-intervention and that declines to 0.00 in the Post-Intervention Third month. The data indicates an improvement in all symptoms taken in the symptom scale post-intervention.

Global Health Status/QoL Values:

The research data of the Global Health Status/QoL scale of six cancer patients has been reflected in Table C.1 presented below in the end. In Table C.1, Quality of life values increase systematically from pre-intervention to post-intervention for all the respondents. For example, in the case of Patient 4, it was 33.33 during pre-intervention and raised progressively to 83.33 in the second-month post-intervention and ultimately it reached 100.00 at the end of the Post-Intervention third month.

Figure C: Mean of the Global Health Status/QoL

Figure C depicts that the pre-intervention mean value of QoL increases from 30.56 to 83.33 in the post-intervention third month which indicates definite improvement post-intervention.

Intervention on symptoms of cancer assessed through EORTC QLQ- BR 23 for Breast Cancer. Patients 1, 3 and 4 have been administered the standard questionnaire EORTC QLQ- BR 23 for assessing the improvement in symptoms of Breast Cancer.

Patient 1:

Figure D: Consolidated View of Symptom and Functional Scale

Figure D depicts that, all four Symptom Scales pre-intervention registered with very high values, have declined gradually and significantly. The Systemic Therapy Side Effect Scale value has declined gradually from a high of 47.62 pre-intervention to 4.76 post-intervention Third month, with a drastic fall from the second month to the intervention's third month. The high value of 77.78 on the Arm symptom scale has come down substantially to 11.11. The high value 66.67 of the Breast Symptom Scale Value has reduced substantially to zero. The low future Perspective Scale value of 33.33 pre-intervention has shown a steep rise to 100 in the post-intervention second month and onwards. Body Image and Sexual Functioning Scale values always remained at 100.00 for all intervention period.

Patient: 3

Figure E: Consolidated view of symptom and functional scales

A synoptic view of the symptom scales and functional scales in Figure E for Patient 3 reveals that all the scale values registered a gradual improvement similar to Figure D of Patient 1. In symptom scales, there is a fall from the pre-intervention to subsequent months and all four Symptom scale values registered zero in the post-intervention third month. For example, the systemic therapy side effects scale score registered post-intervention zero value lowering from a very high value of 95.24. The body image scale and future perspective scale values increased gradually from pre-intervention to a value of 100 post-intervention in the third month.

Patient: 4

Figure F: Consolidated view of symptom and functional scales

Figure F depicts that all the symptom scales/items, systemic therapy side effects, Arm symptoms scale and Breast symptoms scale, show high values in the pre-intervention period and after that, they fell significantly to zero in the post-intervention third month. The upset by hair loss reveals a somewhat static (at a value of 33.33) value for the pre-intervention and post-intervention the first month and the next two months, the respondent chose not to comment on the relevant question underlying this scale.

In the functional scale, the pre-intervention body image scale, the value was 66.67, but thereafter it increased to 100, a 50% increase. For, the future perspective scale, we see that the value of the scale increases gradually from 33.33 in the pre-intervention to 66.67 in the post-intervention first month, a 100% increase, and from 66.67 to 100.00 for the two consecutive months. The sexual function scale values remained static at 100.00 over the intervention period. Sexual Enjoyment Scale under Functional Scales/Items cannot be determined since this respondent chose not to answer the relevant question regarding sexual function.

Patient 2:

Assessment through EORTC QLQ- HL 27 for Hodgkin Lymphoma

Figure G: Overview of all scale (symptom burden, physical condition fatigue, emotional impact, worries -fears) values

In Figure G, an overview of all four scales (symptom burden, physical condition fatigue, emotional impact, worries-fears) revealed the same pattern of post-intervention progressive fall from a very high pre-intervention value, finally registering zero in the post-intervention third month. The values of the Symptom Burden Scale, reduced from 94.44 in the pre-intervention to zero in the post-intervention third month. The Physical Condition/Fatigue scale also exhibits a declining trend in its values from 100.00 in the pre-intervention to 0.00 in the post-intervention third month. Similar is the trend for the Emotional Impact Scale and the Worries/Fears scale.

Qualitative Data:-

PATIENT 1:

Patient 1 was a 70-year-old female, a retired matron of a medical hospital, diagnosed with metastatic breast carcinoma (Invasive Ductal Carcinoma, NST) with extensive lymph node involvement in 2016. In April 2002, she was attuned and empowered with the Spiritual Healing Energy of ‘Reiki’, the Universal Life Force and ‘AUM’, the Eternal Rhythm of the Universe. Despite facing a devastating diagnosis of metastatic breast cancer at the age of 70 years in 2016, she reported significant therapeutic benefits, reassurance and improvement in self-efficacy and minimal side effects of chemotherapy, radiotherapy etc in comparison with other patients of even much younger age by daily practice of Spiritual Energy Healing through ‘Reiki’ and ‘AUM’.

Experiences of Patient 1 in her own words:

“I was guided by my spiritual guide Dr. M.K. Bimal Jee during my cancer treatment journey. I followed his instructions diligently and did self-healing with ‘Reiki’

and the Spiritual method of ‘AUM’ sadhana. I also received a healing touch from my family members who were trained ‘Reiki-attuned healers’ under Dr M K Bimal Sir. I am a medical professional, a retired Matron (Staff Nurse), at Railway Hospital and so I know the pains, trauma and critical challenges faced by cancer patients. But despite undergoing chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and breast removal, I was amazed that I didn't suffer the usual discomforts like nausea, hair loss, Insomnia, loss of appetite, pain, fear of death, Arm symptoms, energy loss and trauma in other parameters of quality of life. My mental strength increased. I truly believe that my commitment to ‘AUM (ॐ)’ and ‘Reiki’ healing practices played a significant role in alleviating detrimental side effects and supporting my well-being during treatment. At the age of 70 years, the journey of treatment of cancer was smooth with the least discomfort compared to other patients who were even much younger than me. I experienced my deep connection with GOD.

PATIENT 2:

Patient 2, a 27-year-old female working as a nurse in a medical hospital was diagnosed with Primary Refractory Hodgkin Lymphoma, Stage 4 in the year 2016 but could not do follow-up medical treatment for 3 years due to a severe financial crisis. She underwent Spiritual Healing and further attunement/empowerment of 'Reiki' and 'AUM' Sadhana in July 2016. She has reported definite positive therapeutic improvement and relief by practising Spiritual Healing with 'Reiki' and 'AUM'.

Experiences of Patient 2 in her own words:

In March-April 2016, I was 27 years old female and, was diagnosed with Primary Refractory Hodgkin Lymphoma Stage 4, a type of lymph node cancer that had spread to my lungs. I was fighting with severe financial constraints. I was scared, I kept thinking that I would die soon without treatment.

At that time, I got the opportunity to get Spiritual Energy Healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM' at Divya Jyoti Sansthan under the selfless guidance of Dr M.K. Bimal Sir. Every day after healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM', I felt very relaxed and light. Within a few days of such spiritual healing my mind became stable. Gradually I got relief from my bodily symptoms. Slowly I started feeling that I may survive and will be cured. Now I started not only doing my daily routine but also doing heavy work. After 3 months, in the month of July 2016, I got attuned to the Divine energy of 'Reiki' and 'AUM' by Spiritual Guide Dr. M.K. Bimal Sir, who also taught us Meditation of Forgiveness (Kshama Dhyaan). Being a medical professional, I knew the dreaded nature of my 4th-stage Primary Refractory Hodgkin Lymphoma so I started doing Spiritual Energy healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM' rigorously as per instructions of Dr. Bimal Sir. I had no money to continue my medical treatment. So, for three years and more, I could not go for follow up and my medical treatment was discontinued. Despite this, I survived, doing my all daily activities very well and continued my occupation. Afterwards, due to some unfavourable situation, I got completely detached from Spiritual Healing 'Reiki' and 'AUM'. Due to this, my physical condition started deteriorating and in February 2019, the symptoms of Hodgkin lymphoma appeared again with a similar set of complaints. On 24.5.2019 I went for a follow-up. The doctor advised 3 cycles of GDP followed by auto SCT. In August 2019 PET scan was done again. There was a large mass in the right lung with a Deauville score of 5.

However, my deteriorated financial condition prevented me from continuing my treatment. So, my treatment again stopped. In this hopeless condition, I again sought help from my Spiritual Guide (Dr. M.K. Bimal Sir). After hearing everything, he told me to stay with my husband temporarily at Divya Jyoti Sansthan, Kolkata so

that the full process of dedicated Spiritual Healing 'Reiki' and 'AUM (ॐ)' may be done. I started getting spiritual healing again at Divya Jyoti Sansthan and felt a lot of improvement.

In January 2020, we came to know that TMC, (Tata Memorial Cancer Research) Kolkata, hospital is being empanelled by the EB health scheme. I applied for that, and finally, I got conventional medical treatments. Surprisingly, due to the spiritual healing of 'AUM' and 'Reiki', I did not suffer from the side effects of medical treatments. And finally, the PET-CT scan report of 27/3/2021 confirmed that no metabolically active disease was seen.

Today, I am completely free from Classical Hodgkin Lymphoma, Refractory.

PATIENT 3:

Patient 3, a 43-year-old woman was diagnosed with "Invasive Ductal Carcinoma" in her right breast lump in 2000. She was given chemotherapy for 4 cycles and undertaken 24 radiations from SSKM hospital. She was attuned and empowered by the Spiritual Healing Energy of 'AUM' and 'Reiki' after which she got a lot of relief from trauma, pain, fear, side effects of chemotherapy and radiation etc and her quality of life improved.

Experiences of Patient 3 in her own words:

"In 2000, I was diagnosed with two malignant tumours, one in the right breast and the other in the uterus. The uterus tumour was like a deuce ball and malignant which was operated on 15th October 2000. The tumour in my right breast was malignant and 2nd stage of Cancer. On 16 February 2001, an operation was done to remove my right breast. After the operation, I went to Tata Memorial Cancer Research, Mumbai for further treatment. Post-operation, I had to go for 4-cycles of chemotherapy. After my first chemotherapy, I suffered severe side effects like severe nausea, heavy hair loss, loss of appetite, depletion of energy etc. My life was totally crippled and devastated. In 2001, During the second chemotherapy, I got attuned by Spiritual Master, Dr. M.K. Bimal Sir in the spiritual process of 'AUM (ॐ)' and 'Reiki' healing. I started doing Spiritual Energy Healing through 'AUM' and 'Reiki' healing. To my utter surprise, I found that this time, I had no side effects from chemotherapy. I had completely lost my appetite, but as I began 'AUM' meditation and 'Reiki' Healing, I regained my appetite, overcame the dreaded fear of losing my life, and renewed hope for the future. After my attunement and practice of Spiritual Energy Healing with 'Reiki' and 'AUM', I did not feel the after-effects of chemotherapy and radiation. I also went to SSKM to take 24 radiations. My well-being and life quality improved a lot and my faith in GOD was restored.

With constant Spiritual Energy healing, I got complete recovery from the dreaded cancer. Still, I do all the Spiritual Healing of 'AUM' and 'Reiki'.

PATIENT 4:

Patient 4, a 57-year-old female, was diagnosed with advanced stage Metastatic breast cancer in 2021. In conjunction with conventional therapy, she incorporated Spiritual Energy Healing through 'AUM' and 'Reiki'. Consistent 'Reiki' and 'AUM' healing sessions were done along with chemotherapy under conventional medical treatment. She reported definite results in the management of side effects of Chemotherapy, reduction in pain, fast recovery, and increase in Inner Energy and quality of life. Notably, despite contracting COVID-19, Spiritual Energy healing 'Reiki' and 'AUM' meditation aided her swift recovery.

Experiences of Patient 4 in her own words:

Facing advanced breast cancer, I turned to the healing power of 'Reiki' and 'AUM' under the guidance of Dr. M.K. Bimal Sir. This helped me through surgery and chemotherapy without the side effects of medical treatment. The miraculous combination of Spiritual Energy healing 'AUM' and 'Reiki' brought high haemoglobin, energy, and stamina during treatment. Fear, anxiety and trauma reduced significantly. I experienced increased mental strength, emotional stability and feeling of well-being. Such a quick positive impact of spiritual energy healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM (ॐ)' amazed everyone, and even when I got COVID, I swiftly recovered. Spiritual meditations and healing under the guidance of revered Guide Dr. M K Bimal Sir resolved all my health issues. I credit 'AUM' and 'Reiki' for my mental strength and quick recovery from the dreaded disease. I felt a sense of deep divine protection during healing.

PATIENT 5:

Patient 5 is a 55-year-old male who was diagnosed with colorectal cancer as moderately differentiated infiltrating adenocarcinoma of the colon (Dukes stage B) in 2002. He underwent conventional cancer treatment, including hemicolectomy, chemotherapy, and other symptomatic treatments along with Spiritual Energy Healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM' meditation.

Experiences of Patient 5 in his own words:

"In September 2002, I was diagnosed with colon cancer. I felt scared, anxious, and helpless suffering from severe pain and discomforts/medical conditions. But then, in July 2004, I met Spiritual Guide Dr. M.K. Bimal Sir, who attuned and empowered me to Spiritual Energy Healing through 'AUM (ॐ)' and 'Reiki'.

As I continued with my medical treatments, I also practised Spiritual Energy Healing of 'Reiki' and 'AUM' regularly. Seeing how well my body responded to the spiritual energy healing was amazing. My whole life condition improved physically, mentally, and emotionally. I got much relief in pain. My fear of death vanished. There was immediate relief from Depression, Tension, and Anxiety resulting in tremendous improvement in day-to-day life conditions. Earlier I was very uncomfortable in mixing with the people but after doing healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM', I started accepting people and gained confidence. My bowel movements became normal, and I could overcome the psychological trauma. My memory and concentration improved a lot. In 2007, I had my last medical check-up, and to my joy, the cancer was gone completely! Not only that, but all my other physical problems also improved. I felt an amazing increase in Inner Strength and confidence within me.

What's more, I found myself much happier and content from within, and my social interactions increased. It's like a whole new transformation happened in me.

PATIENT 6:

Patient 6, a 53-year-old man, was diagnosed with metastatic renal cell carcinoma in 2015 when he was undergoing treatment for pneumothorax. He received attunement with the life force 'Reiki' and the eternal rhythm of 'AUM'. After the sessions of Spiritual healing, he underwent a successful nephrectomy with a good outcome.

Experiences of Patient 6 in his own words:

"In 2015, I faced a daunting diagnosis of cancer in my left kidney, along with lung problems. Feeling overwhelmed under severe trauma, I sought solace in the guidance of Spiritual Guide Dr. M.K. Bimal Sir, who introduced me to the healing power of Spiritual Energy Healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM (ॐ)'. Practising Spiritual Energy healing 'Reiki' and 'AUM (ॐ)', I felt a profound sense of inner peace and strength. Miraculously in just 5 days, my fear of death diminished, and my appetite and sleep improved. I became much more stable emotionally and felt that I would recover and be fully well. I felt conspicuous relief in pain and other symptoms. With each passing day, my health steadily improved, and I regained my zest for life. Heartiest

DISCUSSION:

Significance of the findings:-

Quantitative Analysis for Quality of Life:

The functional scale shows that in the pre-intervention period, the respondents register a low value but as they

progress forward, they register high values. All the respondents have recorded 100% improvement in the post-intervention third month. This shows that Spiritual Energy healing through 'Reiki' and the Spiritual method of 'AUM' has definite positive therapeutic effects on physical, emotional, role, cognitive and social functioning aspects. The table of mean also confirms the positive impact of the intervention.

The symptom scale shows that in the pre-intervention stage, the scores of all the respondents have been very high (many having a value of 100) but it has declined gradually in the third month of the post-intervention period (most of them recorded a value of 0). This shows that after getting attunement and practising Spiritual Energy healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM' problems like fatigue, nausea and vomiting, pain dyspnoea, insomnia, appetite loss and constipation have been mitigated. The mean shows that in the post-intervention stage, the respondents have reported definite relief and recovery from ailments.

The global health status/QOL scale shows that during the pre-intervention period, the values of the respondents have been very low but it has increased considerably post-intervention; increasing from 0 to 75 for patient 2, from 16.67 to 75 for patient 3, from 33.33 to 100 for patient 4 and so on. The mean values show that there were significant improvements in physical and mental aspects.

Quantitative Analysis for Specific Cancer Symptoms:

In the case study of Patients 1,2 and 3, the data collected in EORTC QLQ – BR- 23 (specific for breast cancer) shows that the scores in Systemic therapy side effects, upset by hair loss, arm symptoms, and breast symptoms are very high but the scores have decreased after imparting intervention. The scores have slowly decreased to 0.00/very minimal. In the case of the functional scale, the scores have been low in the pre-intervention stage but in the post-intervention stage, the scores have increased considerably.

The EORTC QLQ - HL 27 (specific for Hodgkin lymphoma) scale shows that during the pre-intervention period, the scores of the Symptom burden scale, Physical condition, Emotional impact scale, Worries/Fears health and Functioning scale have been very high in Patient 4 which diminished to 0.00 after the intervention. All the patients have improved and gained a new hope in life after getting the intervention of Spiritual Energy Healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM' as adjunctive therapy with conventional medical treatments.

Qualitative Analysis:

The testimonials by patients in their own words show that the intervention of Spiritual Energy Healing through 'AUM' and 'Reiki' along with conventional medical

treatments has immensely benefitted the patients. Most importantly, the patients have overcome the fear of death and have experienced a definite enhancement in quality of life. Now they are living healthy lives after surviving the dreaded disease of Cancer.

Implications and Future Research:

The research has a practical implication of using Spiritual Energy Healing 'Reiki' and 'AUM' as adjunctive therapy to conventional medical treatments in hospitals and clinics to provide relief from the side effects of conventional treatments, reduce pains and worries among patients and enhance the quality of life. Health practitioners should also adopt these techniques to give more effective medical care services to cancer patients. Intensive studies with a bigger sample size including other types of cancer can be conducted in the future.

CONCLUSION:

Spiritual Energy healing through 'Reiki' and 'AUM' (ॐ) is therapeutically highly effective as adjunctive therapy to ensure holistic and comprehensive health outcomes. Health practitioners should use these as adjunctive therapies to enable the patients to have sustained recovery and healthy living in the future.

Ethical Considerations:

The researcher abided by the ethical guidelines to conduct this research by protecting the anonymity and confidentiality of the participants. The Research study has been approved by the Ethical Committee, Divya Jyoti Sansthan vide approval No. DJS/EC/01.

Competing Interests:

No competing interests are involved.

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Table A.1: Functional scale of the respondents

Functional scales				Physical functioning scale	Role functioning	Emotional functioning	Cognitive functioning	Social functioning
Name of the Respondent	Patient 1	Month	Pre-intervention	33.33	33.33	58.33	100.00	66.67
			Post-intervention First month	53.33	50.00	100.00	100.00	83.33
			Post-Intervention Second month	80.00	66.67	100.00	100.00	83.33
			Post-Intervention Third month	86.67	83.33	100.00	100.00	83.33
	Patient 2	Month	Pre-intervention	6.67	.00	.00	.00	.00
			Post-intervention First month	40.00	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33
			Post-Intervention Second month	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67
			Post-Intervention Third month	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Patient 3	Month	Pre-intervention	33.33	.00	.00	.00	.00
			Post-intervention First month	66.67	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33
			Post-Intervention Second month	100.00	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67
			Post-Intervention Third month	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Patient 4	Month	Pre-intervention	53.33	66.67	33.33	100.00	50.00

			Post-intervention First month	73.33	66.67	100.00	100.00	83.33
			Post-Intervention Second month	86.67	100.00	100.00	100.00	83.33
			Post-Intervention Third month	93.33	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Patient 5	Month	Pre-intervention	13.33	16.67	.00	16.67	.00
			Post-intervention First month	40.00	33.33	8.33	16.67	.00
			Post-Intervention Second month	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67
			Post-Intervention Third month	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00
	Patient 6	Month	Pre-intervention	60.00	33.33	8.33	100.00	50.00
			Post-intervention First month	66.67	66.67	91.67	83.33	66.67
			Post-Intervention Second month	93.33	83.33	100.00	100.00	83.33
			Post-Intervention Third month	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00

Table B.1: Symptom scale of the respondents

Symptom scales/items			Fatigue	Nausea and vomiting	Pain	Dyspnoea	Insomnia	Appetite loss	Constipation	Diarrhoea	Financial difficulties
Name of the Respondent	Patient 1	Pre-intervention	55.56	.00	83.33	66.67	33.33	66.67	.00	.00	.00
		Post-intervention 1 st month	55.56	.00	66.67	33.33	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00

			Post-Intervention 2 nd month	11.11	.00	16.67	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
			Post-intervention 3 rd month	.00	.00	16.67	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
Patient 2	Month		Pre-intervention	100.00	83.33	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	66.67	66.67	100.00
			Post-intervention 1 st month	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67	33.33	66.67
			Post-Intervention 2 nd month	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	.00	33.33
			Post-Intervention 3 rd month	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
Patient 3	Month		Pre-intervention	100.00	83.33	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	66.67	66.67	100.00
			Post-intervention 1 st month	55.56	66.67	50.00	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67	33.33	66.67
			Post-Intervention 2 nd month	22.22	33.33	16.67	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	.00	33.33
			Post-Intervention 3 rd month	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
Patient 4	Month		Pre-intervention	44.44	.00	83.33	66.67	33.33	66.67	.00	.00	.00
			Post-intervention 1 st month	22.22	.00	33.33	33.33	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
			Post-Intervention 2 nd month	.00	.00	16.67	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
			Post-Intervention 3 rd month	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
Patient 5	Month		Pre-intervention	100.00	100.00	83.33	100.00	100.00	100.00	100.00	33.33	33.33
			Post-intervention 1 st month	77.78	83.33	66.67	66.67	66.67	66.67	100.00	33.33	33.33
			Post-Intervention 2 nd month	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33	33.33
			Post-Intervention 3 rd month	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
Patient 6	Month		Pre-intervention	33.33	.00	50.00	66.67	33.33	66.67	.00	.00	.00

			Post-intervention 1 st month	11.11	33.33	16.67	.00	33.33	33.33	.00	.00	.00
			Post-Intervention 2 nd month	22.22	.00	.00	.00	33.33	66.67	.00	.00	.00
			Post-Intervention 3 rd month	22.22	.00	.00	.00	33.33	66.67	.00	.00	.00

Table C.1: Global health status/QOL

Global health status/QoL				Global health status/QoL
Name of the Respondent	Patient 1	Month	Pre-intervention	50.00
			Post-intervention First month	58.33
			Post-Intervention Second month	83.33
			Post-Intervention Third month	91.67
	Patient 2	Month	Pre-intervention	.00
			Post-intervention First month	33.33
			Post-Intervention Second month	50.00
			Post-Intervention Third month	75.00
	Patient 3	Month	Pre-intervention	16.67
			Post-intervention First month	33.33
			Post-Intervention Second month	58.33
			Post-Intervention Third month	75.00
	Patient 4	Month	Pre-intervention	33.33
			Post-intervention First month	66.67
			Post-Intervention Second month	83.33
			Post-Intervention Third month	100.00
	Patient 5	Month	Pre-intervention	16.67
			Post-intervention First month	33.33
			Post-Intervention Second month	50.00
			Post-Intervention Third month	66.67
	Patient 6	Month	Pre-intervention	66.67
			Post-intervention First month	66.67
			Post-Intervention Second month	83.33
			Post-Intervention Third month	91.67

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